

Local differences in feature importance for the prediction of PM₁₀, O₃ and NO_x using Dresden as example

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Abstract. Due to high yearly casualties, there has been a great effort to model air pollutants with high spatio-temporal resolution. This study uses Dresden as a case study. Additionally to the commonly used meteorological data, the VAMOSlab provides traffic data with high resolution. We investigate the connections with correlation coefficients, mutual information and random forest feature importance. We identify that the traffic volume is an important predictor for the air pollutants, especially NO_x. The findings provide a robust foundation for the development of sophisticated spatio-temporal models aimed at enhancing air quality in urban environments.

Submission Type. case study, analysis

BoK concepts. GS3-4, AM8

Keywords. feature importance, mutual information, urban air quality, machine learning

1 Introduction

2022, over 360,000 premature deaths have been attributed to exposure to air pollutants in the EU member states (European Environment Agency, 2024). The main pollutants are: Particulate Matter (PM₁₀), Ozone (O₃) and Nitrogen Oxides (NO_x). To identify local hot spots and provide detailed warnings to the public or employ effective countermeasures, there has been a great effort for reliable prediction of air pollutants with both chemical transport (Gao and Zhou, 2024) and machine learning models (Bekkar et al., 2021; Petry et al., 2021; Méndez et al., 2023).

Transport and thus traffic plays a leading role for NO_x and PM₁₀. O₃ is mostly a secondary product of photochemi-

cal reactions by NO_x or volatile organic compounds. Intuitively, traffic data would increase the accuracy of the prediction models. However, the availability of quality traffic data with high spatio-temporal resolution is low. In Dresden, the Chair of Traffic Process Automation at TU Dresden operates the VAMOSlab, a data pool with pre-processed traffic data. We analyse the importance of different features for the prediction of air pollutants including traffic volume data.

Table 1. Measurement stations selected

name	location	traffic volume	abbreviation
Bergstraße	urban	high	htv
Winkelmannstraße	urban	low	ltv
Wahnsdorf	rural	very low	bg

2 Methods and Implementation

We utilise a time series of the year 2023. As there is no traffic volume sensor directly at ltv, we choose the closest available. The bg does not measure the traffic volume, thus it is modelled by sampling from a uniform distribution between 0 and 1. Due to problems with the NO₂ sensor at bg, there are no entries available for that year.

2.1 Data and Software Availability

Features and targets are introduced in Tab. 2. Traffic data is available upon request from VAMOSlab (Yan et al., 2024), subject to approval by the City of Dresden Road Administration Office.

Table 2. Original features and targets

feature	unit	source
temperature	°C	LfULG
radiation	$\frac{W}{m^2}$	LfULG
humidity	%	LfULG
atmospheric pressure	hPa	LfULG
wind direction [cosine and sine]		LfULG
wind speed	$\frac{m}{s}$	LfULG
precipitation	$\frac{mm}{m^2}$	DWD
traffic volume		VAMOSlab
target	unit	source
NO concentration	$\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$	LfULG
NO ₂ concentration	$\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$	LfULG
PM ₁₀ concentration	$\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$	LfULG
O ₃ concentration	$\frac{\mu g}{m^3}$	LfULG

2.2 Correlation, Mutual Information and Feature Importance

Pre-processing includes merging all the data sets while excluding values missing in the data set from DWD or LfULG.

The Pearson correlation coefficient (Pearson, 1895) quantifies strength and sign of linear dependencies. Mutual information (MI) additionally computes the strength of non-linear dependencies (Kraskov et al., 2004). The MI of two variables can be conditioned on a third variable. The result will be the amount of information shared by the two variables, not being shared by the third variable (Runge, 2017).

As a model for the regression task, we use a random forest regressor (Ho, 1995) with 100 trees and a maximum depth of ten. The model is chosen due to the sparse data and high explainability. As measurement uncertainty for the air pollutants, we use the legally defined maximum measurement uncertainty (15% for O₃ and NO_x; 25% for PM₁₀).

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Correlation and Mutual Information

The Pearson correlation coefficients in Fig. 1 show dependencies between features like temperature and humidity well. In contrast to MI however, it cannot accurately quantify nonlinear relationships e.g. between the sine and cosine of the wind direction. A high MI can be seen between O₃ and humidity. This is to be expected, because the more vapor is present in the atmosphere, the less O₃ will be created (Ono et al., 2014). The CMI values in Fig. 2 show how much of the information of a current target is exclusively present in the current feature. The high values for the traffic volume indicate a great importance of that feature when trying to predict air pollutants, especially NO_x. Past feature values are expected to also influence the current targets. The total amount of shared information be-

tween features and targets thus will even be higher than suggested by Fig. 2.

3.2 Feature Importance

To determine the feature importance, a random forest regressor is used. In the feature importance (Fig. 3), humidity is in the top three for every place. This aligns well with the dependence between O₃ and humidity identified in Sec. 3.1. Temperature and wind speed, which accounts for transportation effects, also show up in the top positions.

The traffic volume as a feature is only relevant for places with higher traffic volume. This aligns with the expectation that the amount of traffic influences the air pollutant concentration. As expected, with the modelling of the traffic counts as a random number for background, the traffic is the least important feature for prediction. The features used in this work cannot account for air pollution due to agriculture.

The contrast between htv and ltv is of particular interest. The function of the station ltv is to measure the background of the nearby htv, although the traffic volume in ltv is of less importance than in htv. A similar behavior is exhibited by the wind speed feature, which is of high importance for htv and lower for ltv.

4 Conclusion and Outlook

In this work, we investigated the correlation and feature importance of the weather and traffic data for the prediction of air pollutants O₃, NO_x and PM₁₀. We employed the Pearson correlation coefficient and mutual information to quantify dependencies between features and targets. We identified that Pearson correlation coefficients are not sufficient to cover the complexity of the underlying data.

It was determined that traffic volume and wind speed are important features in the prediction of air quality in areas with high traffic volumes. This supports the intuition that traffic data would improve the prediction quality of air pollutants. To identify the effects of traffic, an implementation of a pair of stations of foreground and background such as htv and ltv is very helpful.

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Declaration of Generative AI in Writing

The authors declare that they have used no AI in writing.

Figure 1. Pearson correlation coefficients and MI for individual features of the data set containing the locations htv and ltv. The left panel shows the Pearson correlation coefficients, ranging from -1 for perfect anti correlation to 1 for perfect correlation. The MI is normalized using the information content of the two variables $H(X, Y)$ and can vary between 0 and 1.

Figure 2. Conditional mutual information (CMI) between targets and features conditioned on all other features. The CMI value is given in percent of the total target information for the data set containing the locations htv and ltv.

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Figure 3. Feature importance according to the GINI importance measure for the six different data sets.

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